

Joint Beam Steering and Direct Antenna Multimodulation Using Time-Modulated Arrays

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Abstract—In this article, we introduce a novel architecture-independent technique for time-modulated arrays (TMAs) that enables simultaneous direct-antenna multimodulation (DAMM) and beam steering. We validated the approach across a remarkably broad variety of modulation constellations, confirming its ability to implement arbitrary direct-antenna IQ modulation. This flexibility makes the technique highly suitable for Internet of Things (IoT) applications spanning scenarios that demand either robust communication or high-spectral efficiency, all on a single energy-efficient, low-cost hardware platform. The proposed method operates within the available TMA bandwidth and achieves precise beam steering without relying on computationally intensive optimization algorithms. Unlike previous studies that evaluate TMAs in isolation, we design and characterize a fully integrated transmitter that combines DAMM and beam steering functionalities. The resulting TMA-based DAMM transmitter employs a reduced hardware architecture, delivering both cost and energy savings ideally matched to resource-constrained, low-latency IoT deployments.

Index Terms—Antenna arrays, beam steering, modulation.

I. INTRODUCTION

TRADITIONAL wireless transmitters use quadrature modulators, which involves mixing the analog baseband signal components, in-phase (I) and quadrature-phase (Q), with two 90° out-of-phase versions of the same carrier wave [1, Ch. 5]. If in-phase and quadrature-phase (IQ) modulation and beam steering (BS) are to be performed, conventional transmitters offer two options, shown in Fig. 1(a) and (b), where the antenna (or antenna array) is fed by a

modulated and up-converted radio frequency (RF) signal [2]. In conventional transmitters with BS capability, as shown in Fig. 1(a) and (b), the digital (binary) information must be first converted into its analog (baseband) representation, requiring two analog-to-digital converters (ADCs). The two analog components of the baseband signal, I and Q, are then fed into RF mixers, where they modulate the carrier wave and its orthogonal counterpart [2]. Fig. 1(a) illustrates a direct-conversion transmitter with a phased array. This approach benefits from requiring only one RF chain, but it comes at the cost of reduced flexibility in BS control. On the opposite side, Fig. 1(b) shows the digital beamforming solution, which provides large flexibility in BS control, but at the cost of high complexity and power consumption because it requires one RF chain per antenna element.

A direct antenna modulation (DAM) method offers a significant simplification of the transmitter architecture by employing a fully digital modulation approach. Unlike conventional systems, the binary stream is not converted into its analog baseband representation. Instead, it is delivered directly to the antenna controller, as illustrated in Fig. 1(c), which shows a direct-conversion transmitter with a phased array utilizing variable-gain amplifiers (VGAs) and variable phase shifters (VPSs). This approach results in a simpler and more energy-efficient system architecture compared to conventional transmitters with IQ modulators, as it eliminates the need for frequency mixers and digital-to-analog converters (DACs). However, the use of VGAs and VPSs introduces other issues, such as phase quantization errors and additional insertion losses. Furthermore, these devices are both power-hungry and expensive. Notice that all these drawbacks are critical for battery-powered wireless sensors and Internet of Things (IoT) devices.

To meet the requirements of the IoT domain, the aforementioned disadvantages must be overcome. Theoretical concepts of removing or replacing VGAs with RF switches were presented in [4] and [5], respectively. In this work, we go even further by proposing a DAMM transmitter with BS that is also VPS free. This results in significantly improved power efficiency and hardware complexity reduction. Our design, illustrated in Fig. 1(d), is based on a periodically switched beamforming network (BFN) controlled by periodic sequences—in other words, a time-modulated array (TMA) layout—which can be used to perform DAMM-BS, alleviating insertion

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Fig. 1. (a) Conventional “non-DAM” scheme with analog beamformer [3, Ch. 8]; (b) conventional “non-DAM” scheme with digital beamformer [3, Ch. 8]; (c) conventional “DAM” scheme with both VGAs and VPSs [2]; and (d) proposed architecture of our DAMM-TMA based on switches governed by periodic signals to jointly perform DAMM and beam steering.

losses and quantization errors while minimizing the hardware complexity.

A. State-of-the-Art

DAM is reported quite prolifically in the literature from an experimental point of view. An illustrative example is a prototype which performs on-off keying (OOK) modulation realized by a microstrip patch with diodes placed between the antenna and the ground plane [6], [7] or by an on-off switch located in a feeder of a wire monopole antenna [8]. Utilization of DAM for such a simple modulation scheme brings a significant advantage because it allows for transmitting signals over a range of frequencies well beyond the antenna’s resonant bandwidth [9], [10]. Accordingly, [11] shows a method of generating a binary frequency-shift keying (BFSK) signal exceeding the loop antenna’s impedance bandwidth by using a complementary pair of high-electron mobility transistors (HEMTs). In [12], quadrature phase-shift keying (QPSK) and binary phase-shift keying (BPSK) modulated signals were generated in a monopole antenna driven by a simple circuit consisting of a switch, a transformer and a series inductance. In [13], a two-element antenna array with switchable feeding

lines for BPSK DAM was presented, although without any signal analysis at the communication level. Direct generation of frequency modulated (FM) signals through varactor diode tuning was reported in [14].

In [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], and [14], DAM takes place within the antenna array or its feeding structure. However, according to [15], [16], [17], [18], [19], and [20], DAM can take place also outside the antenna, for instance in its proximity. For example, in [15] a 60-GHz signal radiated by a dipole antenna is modulated by reconfigurable reflectors located under a hemispherical silicon lens. Another approach involves using frequency-selective surfaces (FSS) in the antenna proximity, which can control properties of radiated electromagnetic waves to generate high-order phase-shift keying (PSK) modulated signals [16], [17]. In [18], an amplitude-shift keying (ASK) modulated signal is generated by a two-state gain control of a microstrip antenna with a reconfigurable metasurface layer placed at a distance of 70 mm (0.58 λ). DAM can be realized even in the far-field region by means of reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RISs) [19], [20], [21], [22], [23].

DAM and BS are distinct and well-established technologies which are not usually combined in a single antenna system.

TABLE I
COMPARISON TABLE OF DAM-TMA TRANSMITTERS WITH BS

Ref.	Modulation schemes	Feeding network architecture	f_c (GHz)	B^* (MHz)	Total efficiency	Experimental assessment
[24]	BPSK, QPSK	SP3T switches and fixed 180° phase-shifters	N/A	N/A	low	✗
[25]	QPSK	TMA with SPDT switches and 2-bit phase shifters	N/A	N/A	high	✗
[26]	16-APSK, QPSK	Space-time-coding array	N/A	N/A	low	✗
[27]	FSK	TMA with switched-line phase shifters	N/A	N/A	high	✗
[28]	BPSK, QPSK	SP3T switches and fixed phase shifters	N/A	N/A	low	✗
[29]	BPSK, QPSK	SP4T switches and fixed phase shifters	N/A	N/A	high	✗
[30]	BPSK, QPSK, 16-QAM	TM-LWA in SIW technology with 164 p-i-n diodes	23.5	1.2	low	✓
This work	Arbitrary amplitude and phase	16 patch antennas and 4 SPDT switches	5.6	50.0	high	✓

single-pole triple-throw (SP3T)

single-pole quadruple-throw (SP4T)

single-pole dual-throw (SPDT)

B^* - maximum bandwidth of the transmitted signal without aliasing of the spectral replicas.

N/A - not applicable because a theoretical concept was presented without any experimental verification.

However, the recent literature reveals two joint DAM and BS examples. The first one is an array of DAM transmitters with VPSs that adjust the phase of each signal as in the phased array [15]. The second is based on the subset modulation of the phased array with RF switches and VPSs controlled at the symbol rate [5]. Nevertheless, there are still notable challenges and limitations regarding flexibility, insertion losses, complexity, and cost of both approaches due to VPSs used as a control element. For instance, a b -bit VPS can only offer $360^\circ/2^b$ discrete phases, necessitating $2b$ single-pole dual-throw (SPDT) switches [31], [32] in its circuit topology, which increases power losses and system complexity. The need for simpler and more energy efficient circuits motivated the development of DAM-BS transmitters without VPSs, as the ASK transmitter with four switchable beams presented in [33]. Recent studies demonstrated the feasibility of DAM based on TMAs. Table I gathers the main parameters of direct antenna modulation with time-modulated array (DAM-TMA) transmitters with BS published over the last five years.

In [24], a multicarrier DAMM approach with TMAs is explored, in which two harmonics are utilized for direct BPSK modulation. This DAMM method with TMAs relies on harnessing multiple harmonics, necessitating appropriate windowing of these harmonics. Consequently, the DAMM method becomes closely associated with and dependent on time-modulation efficiency. Furthermore, constructing signal constellations cannot be accomplished through closed formulas, requiring a time-consuming optimization method that conditions the low latency. Unfortunately, this approach only achieves efficiencies¹ below 40% and significantly penalizes the TMA directivity, making it a less desirable option.

Outstanding results were obtained with a time-modulated leaky-wave antenna (TM-LWA) [30], [35] fabricated in the substrate-integrated waveguide (SIW) technology with 164 p-i-n diodes embedded inside 82 slots (2 diodes per slot). TM-LWA operates at the center frequency of 23.5 GHz, which

¹Notice that in Table I, only one reference (other than this work) presents a fabricated prototype with conceptual tests, but without rigorous efficiency measurements. Hence, the only fair way to compare efficiency is by means of theoretical calculations. Moreover, according to [34], theoretical and measured TMA efficiencies show a strong correlation.

is designated for 5G communications. However, because of very low time-modulation frequency ($f_0=1.2$ MHz) only narrowband signals can be transmitted without overlapping with spectral replicas [36]. The DAMM in [35] and [30] is based on space translation introduced to the spatial amplitude envelope. Experiments were conducted for QPSK, 8-PSK, 16-APSK, and 16-QAM. However, the results presented in [37] are without BS. Moreover, p-i-n diodes consume substantial amount of energy and significantly limit the time-modulation frequency. Therefore, in this article the idea of using time-modulation for DAM is further developed with goals of improving the total efficiency and extending the signal bandwidth by proposing a design based on a simple and accessible fabrication technology. While the DAM transmitter with BS is applicable to various wireless communication systems, it is particularly well-suited for IoT devices operating in congested frequency bands. The key advantages of BS in IoT communication include enhanced antenna gain, reduced interference, improved communication reliability, and strengthened physical layer security [38], [39], [40]. Previous research has demonstrated BS antenna arrays without VPSs for IoT applications [41], [42]. However, these designs feature large dimensions and high energy consumption from p-i-n diodes, making them suitable only for relays rather than end devices. Conversely, alternative designs presented in [43] and [44] lack essential feeding networks, which are critical components for practical implementation.

B. Contributions of This Work

The TMA method proposed in this article offers three advantages not provided by existing approaches. First, it is truly suitable for low-latency IoT applications. The reasons are the following.

- 1) The prototype provides a significant higher bandwidth (50 MHz) compared to existing alternatives in the related TMA literature; see Table I for a summary of competing approaches. Indeed, our proposal is the only one valid for low-latency IoT. Bandwidth is critical in IoT applications where delays can lead to security risks or process failures, such as advanced e-health, smart video surveillance, or industrial automation.

- 2) It does not require real-time optimization algorithms to perform the combined DAMM beam steering technique, unlike, for example, [24], [25], [28], [29].
- 3) It includes a comprehensive experimental verification of the prototype following the measurement guidelines suggested in [45], unlike works, such as [5], [24], [25], [26], and [46]. Note that it is a low complexity, switch-only-based prototype that eliminates the need for RF mixers, DACs, VPSs, and VGAs, while demonstrating beam steering with relatively high angular resolution (1.44°).

Second, it enables arbitrary direct antenna IQ modulation, including high order quadrature amplitude modulation (QAM), amplitude and phase-shift keying (APSK), or golden angle modulation (GAM), thereby supporting a wide variety of IoT applications using the same cost- and energy-efficient hardware. More specifically

- 1) The DAMM-TMA technique allows for straightforward generation of spectral efficient modulation schemes, such as GAM or the hexagonal quadrature amplitude modulation (HQAM). Note that, at present, the use of modulation schemes other than frequency-shift keying (FSK) or PSK in IoT with conventional technology is not common, as it requires expensive, complex, and energy-inefficient hardware.
- 2) It also allows the implementation of high order phase shift keying modulations on the same hardware, enabling high bandwidth applications in noisier channels, such as cameras, smart buildings, e-health, and more.

Third, it is architecture-independent, allowing the realization of DAMM and beam steering with any existing TMA hardware without compromising the time modulation efficiency of the original architecture, since only the switching delays are adjusted at the symbol rate.

II. DAM-BS WITH TMAS

A. Efficiency and Radiation Pattern of TMAs

TMAs are antenna arrays equipped with switched time-modulated feeding networks (TM-FNs), offering an attractive alternative to phased arrays that rely on VPSs [47]. TMAs excel in beam steering capabilities by simply adjusting the on-off instants of the switches in their feeding network [34], [48], [49], [50], [51], [52], [53], [54], [55], [56], [57]. This inherent adaptability allows TMAs to significantly enhance signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and error vector magnitude (EVM) not only in line-of-sight communication scenarios [58], but also in multiple-input-multiple-output (MIMO) setups [59], [60].

Let us consider a linear array comprising N isotropic elements with unitary static excitations $I_n = 1$, where $n \in \Gamma = \{1, \dots, N\}$. Each element's excitation is modulated by a periodic pulsed signal $h_n(t)$ with a fundamental period T_0 , realized through a switched TM-FN, as illustrated in Fig. 1(d). In the design of TMAs, new considerations must be taken into account that do not arise in conventional phased arrays due to the presence of radiation harmonics. Consequently, a vital performance metric for TMAs is the time-modulation efficiency, defined as the ratio of the useful power radiated by

TABLE II
CHARACTERISTICS OF HIGH-EFFICIENCY TMAS IN THE LITERATURE IN TERMS OF $\Delta\text{SBR}_{\text{PEAK}}$ [SEE (5)] AND TIME-MODULATION EFFICIENCY η_{TM} [SEE (1)]

Ref.	modulating pulse $h(t)$	architecture	$\Delta\text{SBR}_{\text{PEAK}}$ (dB)	η_{TM} (%)
[54]	quantized sine	6xSPDT+1xSP3T	-16.90	94.96
[61]	quantized sine	4xSPDT	-13.96	91.19
[62]	quantized sine	2xSP4T	-16.90	94.96
[63]	quantized sine	6xSPDT	-16.90	94.49
[64]	quantized linear phase	2xSP3T+2xSPDT	-13.96	91.19
[65]	quantized linear phase	8xSPDT	-16.90	94.94

the TMA ($\mathcal{P}_U^{\text{TM}}$) to the total average power radiated ($\mathcal{P}_R^{\text{TM}}$) and is given by [56]

$$\eta_{\text{TM}} = \frac{\mathcal{P}_U^{\text{TM}}}{\mathcal{P}_R^{\text{TM}}}. \quad (1)$$

To enhance clarity and without loss of generality², we assume that TM-FNs can efficiently exploit only one of the first-order harmonics ($q = -1$ or $q = +1$), while suppressing or strongly attenuating all other harmonics. In simpler terms, the technique presented could be applied to any of the high-efficiency TMA architectures mentioned in the literature and shown in Table II.

In this work, the same basic periodic modulating pulse $h(t)$ will be utilized for all antenna elements. However, the excitation of the n th antenna element will be time-modulated using a time-shifted version of $h(t)$, i.e.,

$$h_n(t) = h(t - D_n) \quad (2)$$

where D_n is a controllable time-delay. Let H_q , $q \in \mathbb{Z}$, represent the exponential Fourier series coefficients of the periodic signal $h(t)$ with period T_0 . The exponential Fourier series coefficients of $h_n(t)$ are then given by

$$H_q e^{-j2\pi f_0 D_n} \quad (3)$$

where $f_0 = 1/T_0$ and they have the same modulus as H_q . If we focus on utilizing the harmonic $q = +1$, the time-modulation efficiency can be expressed as [66, Eq. (14)]

$$\eta_{\text{TM}} = \frac{|H_1|^2}{\sum_{q=-\infty}^{\infty} |H_q|^2} \quad (4)$$

where $|H_1|$ is the magnitude of the Fourier coefficient of $h(t)$ at the harmonic $q = +1$, and the sum is taken over all harmonics.

Considering that $F_q(\theta)$ is the spatial array factor at frequency $f_c + qf_0$, with f_c being the carrier frequency and $\theta \in (-90^\circ, 90^\circ)$ is the angle measured with respect to the x (broadside) axis and on the $x - z$ plane, then $\Delta\text{SBR}_{\text{PEAK}}$ measures the relative level between two patterns: 1) the maximum of the most significant unwanted harmonic (with index u), $|F_u(\theta_{\text{max}})|$; and 2) the maximum of the useful harmonic, $|F_1(\theta_{\text{max}})|$, which we use as our reference pattern because it is stronger than the fundamental harmonic $F_0(\theta_{\text{max}})$ [66]. We can express this mathematically as

$$\Delta\text{SBR}_{\text{PEAK}} = 20 \log \left| \frac{F_u(\theta_{\text{max}})}{F_1(\theta_{\text{max}})} \right| \quad (5)$$

²It is important to note that this approach is applicable to any type of TMA architecture, regardless of its time-modulation efficiency η_{TM} .

where θ_{\max} is the direction in which the array factor amplitude reaches its maximum value.

For our analysis, we make two important assumptions about TMAs: 1) They operate with high time-modulation efficiency (η_{TM}); and 2) they effectively suppress unwanted harmonics, keeping $\Delta\text{SBR}_{\text{PEAK}}$ below certain limits. Table II shows several examples of TMA designs that meet these requirements: time-modulation efficiency (η_{TM}) greater than 91% and harmonic suppression ($\Delta\text{SBR}_{\text{PEAK}}$) better than -13.96 dB. Notice that the modulating pulses $h(t)$ used in these TMAs typically come in two forms: 1) quantized versions of sinusoidal waveforms and 2) pulsed signals with constant amplitude and quantized linear phase. For each TMA design, Table II also specifies the type and number of switches needed for their implementation.

Since the majority of the total energy is transmitted over the first positive harmonic for any of the TMAs specified in Table II, the Fourier series expansion of $h_n(t)$ can be approximated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} h_n(t) &= \sum_{q=-\infty}^{\infty} H_q e^{-jq2\pi f_0 D_n} e^{jq2\pi f_0 t} \\ &\approx H_1 e^{j2\pi f_0 (t-D_n)}. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Therefore, in the case of the TMA-DAM architecture proposed in Fig. 1(d), when transmitting the single-frequency signal $s(t) = e^{j2\pi f_c t}$, where f_c is the carrier frequency, the radiated signal can be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} x(\theta, t) &= \sum_{n=1}^N h_n(t) s(t) = \sum_{n=1}^N h_n(t) e^{j\beta_c z_n \sin \theta} e^{j2\pi f_c t} \\ &\approx \sum_{n=1}^N H_1 e^{j2\pi \left(\frac{z_n}{\lambda_c} \sin \theta - f_0 D_n \right)} e^{j2\pi (f_c + f_0) t} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where z_n represents the position of the n th array element along the z axis, and $\beta_c = 2\pi/\lambda_c$ denotes the wavenumber for a carrier wavelength $\lambda_c = c/f_c$.

After normalizing (7) with respect to H_1 , introducing the notation $F_0 = f_c + f_0$, we obtain

$$\bar{x}(\theta, t) \approx \sum_{n=1}^N e^{j2\pi \left[F_0 t + \left(\frac{z_n}{\lambda_c} \sin \theta - f_0 D_n \right) \right]}. \quad (8)$$

The TMA technique allows us to achieve two important objectives simultaneously: 1) modulate a carrier signal $e^{j2\pi F_0 t}$; and 2) point the maximum radiation pattern toward any desired angle θ_0 . This dual functionality is possible by adjusting the time delays D_n in the periodic modulating waveforms $h_n(t)$. These adjustments control the phase of the signals transmitted by each TMA element, which in turn determines the direction of maximum radiation power.

B. Direct Generation of Phase-Shift Keying Modulations

M -ary phase-shift keying (MPSK) modulation entails phase-shifting the carrier signal based on the symbol to be transmitted. If there are M different symbols s_i , where $i \in \Theta = \{1, \dots, M\}$, a phase shift of $\pi(2i-1)/M$ is applied to

the carrier signal during the symbol interval T_s , corresponding to the specific symbol $s_i = e^{j(\pi(2i-1)/M)}$ being transmitted.

To steer the TMA useful harmonic beam pattern toward a specific direction θ_0 while transmitting a symbol s_i belonging to an MPSK modulation alphabet (where $i \in \Theta$), we can adjust the time delays D_n for each antenna element $n \in \Gamma$ over a symbol time T_s . Our method aims to achieve a twofold objective: 1) to direct the radiation beam toward a specific direction; and 2) synthesize and radiate a particular MPSK data symbol.

By analyzing (7), if we adjust D_n according to the following equation:

$$e^{j2\pi f_0 D_n} = e^{j \left(2\pi \frac{z_n}{\lambda_c} \sin \theta_0 - \frac{\pi(2i-1)}{M} \right)} \quad (9)$$

and then substitute (9) into (8), taking into account (8), we can derive the transmitted signal over a symbol time (noting that D_n does not change for this interval)

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{x}(\theta, t) &\approx e^{j \left(2\pi F_0 t + \frac{\pi(2i-1)}{M} \right)} \sum_{n=1}^N e^{j2\pi \frac{z_n}{\lambda_c} (\sin \theta - \sin \theta_0)} \\ &\approx s_i e^{j2\pi F_0 t} F(\theta) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where $0 \leq t < T_s$, $T_s \gg T_0$. The term $F(\theta)$ represents the TMA's spatial array factor, given by

$$F(\theta) = \sum_{n=1}^N e^{j2\pi \frac{z_n}{\lambda_c} (\sin \theta - \sin \theta_0)}. \quad (11)$$

If the TMA exploits the harmonic $q = -1$, (10) remains valid with some minor changes. In this case, F_0 is given by $F_0 = f_c - f_0$, and (7) becomes

$$x(\theta, t) \approx \sum_{n=1}^N H_{(-1)} e^{j2\pi \left(\frac{z_n}{\lambda_c} \sin \theta + f_0 D_n \right)} e^{j2\pi (f_c - f_0) t}. \quad (12)$$

As a result, the condition in (9) changes to

$$e^{j2\pi f_0 D_n} = e^{j \left(-2\pi \frac{z_n}{\lambda_c} \sin \theta_0 + \frac{\pi(2i-1)}{M} \right)}. \quad (13)$$

In each symbol interval, the useful harmonic beam pattern at frequency F_0 can be steered toward a specific direction θ_0 , resulting in a maximum power radiated beam pattern when transmitting an M -PSK symbol s_i . This steering is achieved by imposing the carrier signal $e^{j2\pi F_0 t}$ to have a phase shift $\pi(2i-1)/M$. The phase adjustment is determined by the normalized time values $\bar{D}_n = D_n/T_0 \in [0, 1)$, as shown in (9).

The number of possible discrete values of \bar{D}_n , achieved by the TM-FN proposed in Fig. 1(d), is dependent on the clock speed of the control unit [54]. Specifically, if the clock period is T_{ck} , then the number of possible phase steps will be T_0/T_{ck} , resulting in $360^\circ/(T_0/T_{\text{ck}})$ different quantized phases. For example, setting $T_0 = 2^{10} T_{\text{ck}} \approx 1000 T_{\text{ck}}$ yields a resolution equivalent to that of a 10-bit VPS.

C. Direct Generation of Arbitrary Amplitude and Phase-Shift Keying Modulation

IoT standards, for example IEEE 802.15 (Bluetooth) and IEEE 802.15.4 (ZigBee), use low-order PSK modulations,

such as offset quadrature phase-shift keying (OQPSK) or $\pi/4$ -DQPSK. However, if a higher spectral efficiency is required, then the corresponding improved performance is obtained with amplitude and phase-shift keying modulation schemes, such as APSK, QAM, and GAM [67].

APSK signals can be generated in DAM-TMA in a similar way as MPSK, i.e., by setting appropriate values of delays D_n . Finding these values from (7) is analytically intractable and requires nonlinear programming or global optimization algorithms. Alternatively, we used the full-search algorithm to calculate all possible configurations and select only the results which correspond to the required constellation diagram. Numerical results for 16-APSK, as a representative example of the amplitude and phase-shift keying modulation, are given in Section III-B.

III. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

A. Quadrature Phase-Shift Keying Modulation With Beam Steering

To bridge the gap between theoretical analysis and experimental measurements, we conducted numerical simulations to compare the theoretical modeling with the actual behavior of different TMA configurations that jointly perform QPSK DAM and beam steering. We considered a TMA with $N = 4$ isotropic elements spaced a half-wavelength ($\lambda_c/2$) apart, which are time-modulated using the high-efficiency TM-FN schemes listed in Table II. The carrier frequency is $f_c = 5.6$ GHz, and the fundamental frequency of the periodic pulsed signal is $f_0 = 50$ MHz (hence, $T_0 = 20$ ns). The TMA operates as a QPSK modulator ($M = 4$) with a symbol period $T_s = 100 \mu\text{s}$.

We consider a TMA that exploits the harmonic $q = -1$ and examine three different scenarios where the array transmits the symbols of the QPSK constellation in the maximum radiation pattern direction for three different angles: $\theta_0 = 0^\circ$, $\theta_0 = -30^\circ$, and $\theta_0 = 30^\circ$.

Considering (9), or the version given in (13) for $q = -1$, we calculate the corresponding time delays D_n applied to the pulses at each antenna element to directly modulate each QPSK symbol in the TMA for each scenario. For example, if $\theta_0 = 0^\circ$, we obtain $D_1 = 2.5$ ns, and hence, $\bar{D}_1 = D_1/T_0 = 1/8$. If $\theta_0 = -30^\circ$, we obtain $D_1 = 7.5$ ns, and hence, $\bar{D}_1 = D_1/T_0 = 3/8$. Figs. 2–4 plot the D_n values that enable QPSK DAM while performing beam steering toward the considered directions.

B. Amplitude and Phase-Shift Keying Modulation With Beam Steering

For this discussion, let us consider a DAM-TMA with $n = 4$ switches and delays ranging from 0 ns to 20 ns in steps of 80 ps, which gives 250^4 possible configurations in total. The amplitude and phase of a signal generated with each configuration toward any angle θ_0 is calculated with (7). Results form a domain of all feasible discrete IQ symbols. As can be noticed from Fig. 5(a), the generation of virtually all symbols is possible, which is due to a small step size of the programmable delay lines (PDLs) (only 80 ps with respect

Fig. 2. (a) Adjusted values of \bar{D}_n to directly modulate each QPSK symbol s_i while simultaneously directing the maximum of its power radiated pattern toward the broadside direction $\theta_0 = 0^\circ$ in a 4-element TMA; (b) relative power radiated pattern (with respect to the maximum of the useful harmonic, $|F_1(\theta_{\max})|$) for all symbols s_i when \bar{D}_n are set as in (a).

to the modulation period $T_0 = 20$ ns). PDLs are key devices in our DAM-TMA approach which are integrated inside the control unit of Fig. 1(d) and explained in detail in the next section, conveniently supported by Fig. 8. Notice that in our case PDLs is 3D3438Z-80 [68]. From the domain of all feasible IQ symbols we form a codebook by selecting only the points which correspond to the desired modulation scheme, such as QAM, APSK, and GAM. The codebook defines values of switching delays which cause: 1) generation of given modulation scheme toward θ_0 , 2) beam-steering toward θ_0 . Let us assume that $\theta_0 = 0^\circ$ and the required modulation is 16-APSK as illustrated in Fig. 5(b). Fig. 6 shows sixteen DAM-TMA radiation patterns, one per symbol. One may notice that the main beam is always pointing at $\theta = 0^\circ$, although its amplitude can be suppressed to facilitate the two-state amplitude modulation of 16-APSK. Corresponding normalized delays are illustrated in Fig. 7.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL ASSESSMENT

A. Measurement Setup

The DAMM method presented in this article can be applied to any TMA architecture, as it relies solely on controlling time delays in the antenna's periodic modulating pulses. To experimentally validate this approach, we implemented a TMA module incorporating patch antennas and SPDT switches, as illustrated in Fig. 8. Note that the antenna symbol in Fig. 8 represents an arbitrary antenna or subarray. In fact, the prototype presented in Fig. 9(b) uses two series-fed patch antennas as a single element. Therefore, even though the

Fig. 3. (a) Adjusted values of \bar{D}_n to directly modulate each QPSK symbol s_i while simultaneously directing the maximum of its power radiated pattern toward the direction $\theta_0 = -30^\circ$ in a 4-element TMA; (b) relative power radiated pattern for all symbols s_i when \bar{D}_n are set as in (a).

Fig. 4. (a) Adjusted values of \bar{D}_n to directly modulate each QPSK symbol s_i while simultaneously directing the maximum of its power radiated pattern toward the direction $\theta_0 = 30^\circ$ in a 4-element TMA; (b) relative power radiated pattern for all symbols s_i when \bar{D}_n are set as in (a).

prototype has 16 patches, it actually consists of eight elements. We selected this TMA design because it achieves the highest combination of signal bandwidth and realized gain among all experimental TMAs reported in the literature to date. For a detailed analysis of its performance, see [34].

Two types of signals are processed within the module: RF signals (in the gigahertz range) and digital control signals (in the megahertz range). Fig. 8 illustrates these signal paths, where the RF signal paths are marked with thick lines, and digital control signal paths are represented by thin lines. Additionally, double lines indicate the serial interface between the microcontroller unit and the PDLs.

- 1) *RF Signals*: A 5.6-GHz sinusoidal carrier wave from an external RF generator is delivered to a uniform four-branch microwave power divider. Each output of the power divider is connected to an SPDT RF switch. The module utilizes four ADRF5020 ultrafast switches [69], selected for their very short rise/fall time of 2 ns. These switches feature alternatively controlled outputs, meaning that only one output is active at a time, while the other remains terminated to a matched load. The switches are used to alternate the RF signal between pairs of oppositely polarized patch antennas. As a result, each antenna element is excited with a pulsed RF signal, where the start and end moments of the RF pulses serve as degrees of freedom, enabling flexible control over the radiation pattern.
- 2) *Digital Signals*: The RF switches are controlled by periodic rectangular waveforms (modulating signals) with 50% duty cycles. According to the TMA theory,

Fig. 5. Complex diagram showing: (a) all feasible symbols (b) selected symbols forming 16-APSK modulation scheme. Calculated for $\theta = 0$.

the pulse repetition frequency should be higher than twice the transmitted signal bandwidth [70]. Therefore, for most IoT applications, even the frequency of 1 MHz would be sufficient. However, in our module an excessive modulation frequency of 50 MHz is chosen to demonstrate the full potential of the ultrafast AD5020 RF switch. In consequence, the distance between sidebands illustrated in Fig. 10 is broadened, allowing for potential transmission of wideband signals without any aliasing of the spectral replicas. To enable independent command of the switches, the control signal is split into four paths using a fan-out clock buffer. Each output of the buffer gives a copy of the 50 MHz clock signal, which is delayed in PDL by a value ranging from 0 ns to 20.4 ns, with a step of 80 ps. The PDLs are programmed by a microcontroller unit, with their settings updated

Fig. 6. Complex radiation patterns of DAMM-TMA (amplitude and phase plotted with different lines) used for the generation of 16-APSK symbols toward $\theta_0 = 0^\circ$. (a)–(h) Correspond to symbol labels in Fig. 5(b).

Fig. 7. Values of \bar{D}_n resulting in radiation pattern presented in Fig. 6.

at the symbol rate. The independently delayed clock signals control the operation of the switches: a low-state enables the first RF output and a high-state enables the second RF output. Hence, the antennas are excited with pulsed RF signals maintaining the abovementioned 50% duty cycle, while the pulse positions in the time domain are delayed by D_n .

The DAMM-TMA module operates at the center frequency $f_c = 5.6\text{GHz}$ with the time-modulation period of $T_0 = 20\text{ns}$. PDLs embedded inside the DAM-TMA module allow a minimal delay step of $T_{ck} = 80\text{ps}$, resulting in a minimal feasible phase-change of $360^\circ/(T_0/T_{ck}) = 1.44^\circ$, which yields a resolution equivalent to that of a 16-bit phase-shifter. Considering that the maximal quantization error of the selected PDLs is $\pm 0.72^\circ$ [68], the DAM-TMA can be used to generate BPSK, QPSK, 8-PSK, 16-PSK, 32-PSK, 64-PSK, and 128-PSK signals, assuming a noise-free channel and a perfect carrier synchronization between the transmitter and the receiver.

The experimental setup is shown in Fig. 9(a). The transmitter includes a signal generator (Rohde & Schwarz SMBV100A) and the DAM-TMA. The receiver utilizes a

Fig. 8. Diagram of DAMM-TMA transmitter under test.

signal analyzer (Agilent E4440A) and a vector signal analyzer software running on a personal computer. During the experiments, the signal generator served as the source of a 5.6-GHz single-tone signal. The spectrum analyzer was used to down convert the received the signal and to demodulate it to IQ baseband samples. Fig. 10 displays the measured power spectrum of a signal generated by the DAMM-TMA under test. Due to the modulation period of 20 ns, harmonics appeared at multiples of 50 MHz around the carrier frequency of 5.6 GHz. In order to demodulate a single harmonic, the spectrum analyzer was configured with a frequency span narrower than the time modulation frequency and its center frequency was

Fig. 9. Experimental setup. (a) Overview of the equipment. (b) Anechoic chamber.

Fig. 10. Signal spectrum measured at the output of DAMM-TMA excited by 5.6 GHz carrier. Harmonics are not symmetric in respect to the center frequency when the BS is enabled. A higher level of $q = -1$ with respect to $q = +1$ indicates that the angular direction of the main beam associated to $q = -1$ is closer to the direction of the signal source.

set to 5.55 GHz or 5.65 GHz to demodulate the first negative ($q = -1$) or positive ($q = +1$) harmonic, respectively. The vector signal analyzer software was used for digital carrier synchronization, symbol synchronization, and symbols-to-bits demapping, allowing for accurate evaluation of the experimental results.

The DAMM-TMA transmitter was thoroughly tested to evaluate its capability to generate various amplitude and phase-shift keying modulation schemes. Fig. 11 shows a few selected results obtained for modulation schemes which are typically used in IoT, i.e., QPSK, 8-PSK, 16-PSK, and 16-APSK. The observed results positively verify the theoretical concepts drawn in Sections II-B and II-C. A detailed description of the measurement methodology is given in subsequent Sections IV-B and IV-C for QPSK with beam steering disabled and enabled, respectively.

Fig. 11. IQ samples generated by DAMM-TMA transmitter after demodulation: (a) QPSK, (b) 8-PSK, (c) 16-PSK, and (d) 16-APSK.

TABLE III
CONFIGURATION OF PDLs FOR QPSK AND THE BROADSIDE BEAM

	Bits	Symbol phase (deg)	Delays (ns)			
			D_1	D_2	D_3	D_4
s_1	00	45	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
s_2	01	135	5.04	5.00	5.04	5.00
s_3	11	-135	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00
s_4	10	-45	15.04	15.00	15.04	15.00

B. Broadside Beam and Direct Generation of QPSK

To generate QPSK symbols and fix the antenna beam toward the broadside direction, the delays were configured according to Fig. 2(a). The actual values applied in the experimental trials are given in Table III and match Fig. 2 with two differences: 1) all normalized delays were shifted by $-1/8$; and 2) due to the hardware related constraints, delays D_1 and D_3 were set to (5.04 ns instead of 5 ns, and 15.04 ns instead of 15 ns), respectively. The first difference simplifies the hardware configuration and has virtually no impact on the transmission, as the demodulator performs automatic phase-shift compensation and detects symbols based on the relative phase change. The second difference introduces an inaccuracy of 40 ps, which is less than 1% of $T_0 = 20$ ns and can be considered as negligible. During the experimental assessment the binary sequence 00011110 was repeatedly transmitted by changing the delays according to Table III. PDLs were updated every 102 μ s, resulting in a symbol rate of 9.8 ksymbol/s. The baseband symbols received at frequencies corresponding to $q = -1$ and $q = +1$ (5.55 GHz and 5.65 GHz, respectively) are presented on complex planes in Fig. 12. Although they seem similar, the order of the symbols is different. At 5.55 GHz ($q = -1$), the phases of the received symbols were changing consecutively with a $\pi/2$ step, yielding the symbol sequence (s_1, s_2, s_3, s_4) which corresponds to 00011110, as expected. However, according to Fig. 13, which shows 16 symbols received during 1.6 ms at 5.65 GHz, the sequence at the harmonic $q = +1$ was (s_2, s_1, s_4, s_3). This observation reveals an interesting relationship between the symbols generated over the harmonics $q = -1$ and $q = +1$, which are complex conjugates. Hence, only the $q = -1$ harmonic is correctly modulated and can be faithfully received.

 Fig. 12. Symbols generated by DAMM-TMA at: (a) $q = -1$ and (b) $q = +1$.

 Fig. 13. IQ samples in the time domain for the broadside beam configuration at $\theta = 0^\circ$ and $q = +1$: amplitude (top) and phase (bottom).

However, symbols demodulated from the $q = +1$ harmonic could be exploited as redundant information.

Fig. 14(a) shows the measured EVM and radiation pattern for our DAMM-TMA when generating a QPSK signal with its main beam directed toward broadside ($\theta_0 = 0^\circ$ irc). The highest signal quality, indicated by the lowest EVM, was measured within an angular range of θ from -20° irc to 20° irc.

The received symbol constellations are shown in Fig. 14(b) through Fig. 14(e). It is clear that the worst case is at -29° , as it is near the null of the power density level. Even at -40° (where the signal is near -15 dBm below the maximum) the constellation is well-formed still. This is applicable to the other cases (Figs. 15 and 16) as well. This behavior, known as directional modulation (DM) [2], [15], [71], enhances physical layer security by making the signal difficult to intercept from unintended angles.

C. Beam Steering and Direct Generation of QPSK

The experimental trials were extended to exploit DAMM with beam steering. Tables IV and V show the configurations of the PDLs, which were used to generate QPSK symbols and steer the beam toward -30° and $+30^\circ$, respectively. One can notice that the delay progression is not ± 5 ns as calculated in Section III, but ± 6 ns. This is because isotropic elements are assumed in (7) and the element factor is not considered. In the case of patch antennas, the element factor can be approximated as $\cos^2(\theta)$ [72]; hence, the delay progression required to obtain the anticipated steering angle must be increased.

 TABLE IV
 CONFIGURATION OF PDLs FOR QPSK AND -30° -BEAM

	Bits	Symbol phase (deg)	Delays (ns)			
			PDL 1	PDL 2	PDL 3	PDL 4
s_1	00	45	0.00	6.00	12.00	18.00
s_2	01	135	5.04	11.04	17.04	3.04
s_3	11	-135	10.00	16.00	2.00	8.00
s_4	10	-45	15.04	1.04	7.04	13.04

 TABLE V
 CONFIGURATION OF PDLs FOR QPSK AND $+30^\circ$ -BEAM

	Bits	Symbol phase (deg)	Delays (ns)			
			PDL1	PDL2	PDL3	PDL4
s_1	00	45	0.00	14.00	8.00	2.00
s_2	01	135	5.04	19.04	13.04	7.04
s_3	11	-135	10.00	4.00	18.00	12.00
s_4	10	-45	15.04	9.00	13.04	7.04

Measurements of the radiation pattern, EVM, and IQ samples received at the frequency corresponding to $q = -1$ are presented in Figs. 15 and 16, for $\theta_0 = +30^\circ$ and $\theta_0 = -30^\circ$, respectively. We observe that the behavior fulfills the expectations, i.e., when the radiation pattern is maximum the EVM is minimum and vice versa.

V. DISCUSSION

Unsophisticated antenna systems lack directional control over the spatial propagation of their radiated electromagnetic waves, leaving IoT networks vulnerable to signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) degradation during high network congestion or deliberate jamming attacks. While steerable antenna arrays offer enhanced security and network resilience [38], their implementation presents a significant challenge: the increased complexity of transceiver electronics conflicts with the fundamental requirements of IoT sensor nodes, which demand compact-size and cost-effective solutions [40].

As shown in Fig. 1, the most common types of transmitters which support simultaneous generation of digitally modulated signals and dynamic control of the antenna radiation pattern (i.e., beam steering) includes as follows.

- 1) Quadrature modulator transmitter with phased array.
- 2) Digital beamforming transmitter with multiple quadrature modulators.
- 3) DAM phased array.
- 4) DAMM-TMA with beam steering (this work).

In this discussion we will compare our design to 1) and 3), taking into consideration cost, energy consumption, and computational complexity as the major criteria. The digital beamforming transmitter with multiple quadrature modulators is deliberately not included due to its high power consumption and hardware complexity, which is far beyond IoT requirements [73].

A. Energy Consumption and Components Cost

The comparison is based on representative examples of crucial components required in each technology.

Fig. 14. Results of measurements at $q = -1$ for the broadside-beam scenario ($\theta_0 = 0^\circ$) with direct modulation of a QPSK signal: (a) radiation pattern and EVM; (b) to (d) diagrams of received IQ symbols for arbitrarily chosen angles θ .

Fig. 15. Results of measurements at $q = -1$ for the -30° -beam and direct modulation of a QPSK signal: (a) radiation pattern and EVM; (b) to (d) diagrams of received IQ symbols for arbitrarily chosen angles θ .

TABLE VI
CRUCIAL COMPONENTS OF THE QUADRATURE MODULATOR
TRANSMITTER WITH PHASED ARRAY

Components	Ref.	Qty	Energy consumption	Unit cost*
VPSs	[74]	N	$N \times 48 \text{ mW}$	161 USD
VGAs	[75]	N	$N \times 330 \text{ mW}$	60 USD
DACs	[76]	2	$2 \times 0.3 \text{ W}$	30 USD
Quad. mod.	[77]	1	1 W	12 USD
Total for $N = 4$:			3.1 W	956 USD

*Values obtained in July 2025, and may vary.

1) Quadrature modulator transmitter with phased array (Table VI): N units of VPSs [74], N units of VGAs [75], two DACs [76], and one quadrature modulator [77].

2) DAM with phased array (Table VII): N VPSs [74], and N VGAs [75].

3) DAMM-TMA transmitter with beam steering (Table VIII): N PDLs [68], N RF switches [78], and a clock fan-out buffer [79].

The total energy consumption and cost were estimated by analyzing the individual requirements of each component, as shown in Tables VI–VIII. Results indicate that the DAMM-TMA with beam steering technology outperforms conventional solutions in both cost and energy efficiency. This is primarily due to the replacement of complex and power-hungry VGAs and VPSs (highly sensitive and precise components with complex topology operating in the RF

Fig. 16. Results of measurements at $q = -1$ for the $+30^\circ$ -beam and direct modulation of a QPSK signal: (a) radiation pattern and EVM; (b) to (d) diagrams of received IQ symbols for arbitrarily chosen angles θ .

TABLE VII
CRUCIAL COMPONENTS OF THE DAM PHASED ARRAY

Components	Ref.	Qty	Energy consumption	Unit cost*
VPSs	[74]	N	$N \times 48$ mW	161 USD
VGAs	[75]	N	$N \times 330$ mW	60 USD
Total for $N = 4$:			1.51 W	884 USD

*Values obtained in July 2025, and may vary.

TABLE VIII
CRUCIAL COMPONENTS OF THE DAMM-TMA
TRANSMITTER (THIS WORK)

Components	Ref.	Qty	Energy consumption	Unit cost*
PDLs	[68]	N	$N \times 6.6$ mW	23 USD
RF switches	[78]	N	$N \times 1$ mW	0.5 USD
Clock fanout buffer	[79]	1	86 mW	6 USD
Total for $N = 4$:			0.03 W	100 USD

*Values obtained in July 2025, and may vary.

domain) with simpler and more efficient PDLs and RF switches.

Furthermore, the proposed approach shifts the modulation process from the analog (RF) to the digital (control) domain, allowing for the use of less complex and more effective components, hence reducing both system complexity and power consumption. According to our estimations, the DAMM-TMA is approximately ten times less expensive and requires only about 1% of the energy consumed by a quadrature modulator transmitter with a phased array.

In addition to these advantages, the DAMM-TMA provides superior angular resolution. While traditional phased arrays are limited by the resolution of VPSs, such as the 5.625° step size of the device in [74], our solution achieves angular resolution better than 1.4° , which would be impractical using conventional digital phase shifters.

Although the initial component costs of the DAMM-TMA may seem high (see Table VIII), they can be significantly

reduced through large-scale production and the adoption of complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (CMOS) integration technologies.

B. Computational Complexity

The use of baseband modulation in existing non-DAM transmitters, as shown in Fig. 1(a) and (b), inevitably increases computational complexity, particularly in the case of the digital beamformer [Fig. 1(b)], which requires a dedicated RF chain per antenna. Contrarily, DAMM schemes presented in Fig. 1(c) and (d) offer greater computational efficiency. Once the initial calibration and PDL calculations are completed, the results are stored in a lookup table, which contains the necessary delay values for transmitting each symbol –out of an alphabet of M symbols– in a given direction. If the TMA can steer to R_a possible angles, the lookup table will contain $M \times R_a$ entries. Additionally, since no time-consuming optimization algorithms are needed, our approach is particularly well-suited for high-mobility, low-latency scenarios, where excessive computational delays may risk the validity of the DAMM-BS method.

VI. CONCLUSION

This work has introduced a novel, architecture-independent TMA technique capable of performing simultaneous DAMM and BS, specifically suitable for low-latency IoT applications. Beyond its advantageous bandwidth and response time the proposed method demonstrates robust multimodulation capabilities achieved without relying on optimization algorithms. These enable dynamic tradeoffs between communication robustness and spectral efficiency across the diverse IoT application landscape, all while using the same energy-efficient and low-cost hardware platform.

Moreover, the proposed approach has been validated through comprehensive experimental testing using a functional prototype, confirming the practical feasibility and effectiveness of the technique as well as the validity of all the performance values.

We hope that this contribution will serve as a catalyst for continued research in this area, encouraging the development of novel methodologies and technological innovations aimed at advancing low-latency IoT systems.

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